

DMP Assistant: Stabilizing for the Future

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DMP Assistant

- A Canadian-focused tool for creating data management plans
- Exists presently as a fork of the DMP Roadmap codebase produced in collaboration through DCC
- Initially launched around 2014, it has gone through an evolution in both platform and management

The early days

- Portage Network launches a tool at assistant.portagenetwork.ca
- Portage Network largely relies on a group at the University of Alberta as a partner to keep the platform moving
- Principally supported by a group of RDM practitioners, principally engaged librarians, through the DMP Expert Group

Decisions, decisions

- Around 2019-20, a decision was made to pursue development independent of existing arrangements through an open-source collaboration
- With 2 FTE developers, this proved to be a challenge

A Shifting Landscape

- In 2020-2021, Portage Network merges into the Digital Research Alliance of Canada (the Alliance)
- Former Portage Network activities become part of the Research Data Management (RDM) team
- Continued partnership with the University of Alberta
- In addition to RDM, the Alliance supports many initiatives in Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI)
 - National compute, including enhancements and access to national compute clusters
 - National cybersecurity
 - Supporting initiatives like ExCANFAR, which is part of the SKA Global initiative

Stabilization of the DMP Assistant

- In 2023, a two-year project is struck by the Alliance with funding from the Department of Innovation, Science, and Economic Development (ISED)
- One initiative among 3 RDM specific initiatives is the DMP Assistant, which has fallen badly out of step with code-base collaborators
- DMP Assistant multi-year funding program was for stabilization of the platform
- Expansion of the team from 2 FTE developers to 2.5
- We're coming up on the end of our two years (our fiscal year ends March 31)

MYFP: Expectation

MYFP: Reality

The Future for DMP Assistant

- The Alliance remains committed to the service as part of a suite of offerings
- DMP Assistant is making plans for the years to come
- Migration to nationally-managed infrastructure that can scale with the platform
 - Kubernetes deployment through our partners at the University of Victoria for greater scalability and security
- Engagement with our funding agencies to ensure the platform meets the needs of researchers
- Future engagement with maDMP

A major goal for the next year:

Return to basics

Enhance our existing relationships, and return to the focus to a high-quality offering for Canadian researchers

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